

BEHAVIOUR OF A FIBER REINFORCED RUBBER
UNDER THE OFF-AXIS TENSILE IMPACT

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ABSTRACT

The behaviour of the unidirectional nylon cord reinforced rubber (NCRR) under the off-axis tensile impact was experimentally studied with a pendulum tensile impact setup and a new direct measuring device of impact force and deformation. Based on the experimental results, the effects of strain rate, off-axis angles, and component properties on the strength, stiffness and stress-strain relationship were analysed.

INTRODUCTION

The fiber reinforced rubber has wide applications in various industry branches, e.g. tyres, diaphragms, air cushions, inflatable rubber boats etc. Unfortunately, its properties, especially the dynamic ones, have not been fully studied.

Fig.1 Experiment equipment.

Fig.2 Diagram of work of whole facilities.

To study the dynamic behaviour of the unidirectional NCRR under off-axis impact, a pendulum tensile impact set-up was employed. This set-up was originally designed for indirect measuring impact force and deformation. To avoid the problems incurred by indirect measurement, a piezoelectric crystal was used as a force sensor. To accommodate the large deformation, a simple deformation measuring device was designed and fabricated. The experimental results show that these new devices are fairly satisfactory. With these specially designed equipments, the effects of strain rate, component properties and off-axis angles on strength, stiffness and stress-strain relationship of NCRR were analysed.

EXPERIMENT

The specimens were cut from a single ply of the NCRR into the size of 120×12×1 mm. Their gauge length is 30mm. The total number of the specimens is 125.

Fig. 1 shows the experimental equipment employed in this study. Fig.2 shows schematically how the whole facilities work. Four different impact velocities: $V_I=3\text{ms}^{-1}$, $V_{II}=4\text{ms}^{-1}$, $V_{III}=5\text{ms}^{-1}$, $V_{IV}=5.4\text{ms}^{-1}$ can be achieved with the pendulum tensile impact set-up. Fig.3 is a picture to show the arrangement of the force sensor and the deformation measuring device. The impact force is measured in terms of electric voltage which is magnified with a preamplifier and input into a transient wave recorder. The main part of the device for deformation measurement is a slipping resistor. The elongation of the specimen is measured in terms of its electrical resistance change. And the histories of the force and deformation are finally drawn with a X-Y recorder.

Fig.3 Arrangement of measuring force and deformation devices.

ANALYSIS OF EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

1. Simple tension results

Fig.4 shows the force history and the deformation history curves

Fig.4 Experimental curves of force histories and deformation histories of 0° specimens under different velocities $V_I, V_{II}, V_{III}, V_{IV}$.

Fig.5 Stress-strain curves of 0° specimens with different velocities and static test.

Table 1 Strengths and stiffnesses of NCRR under tensile impact

V	V_I	V_{II}	V_{III}	V_{IV}	Static
\bar{E} s^{-1}	61.8	87.5	90.7	107.6	
σ_{max} MPa	147.84	137.93	135.60	116.14	213.20
ϵ_{max} %	42.78	42.00		41.95	21.00
\bar{E}^a GPa	0.586	0.570	0.595	0.585	1.015
EN MPa	33.07	30.06	30.43	32.52	23.68

a) \bar{E} indicate the average values of modulus of elasticity corresponding to the peak load.

for the 0° specimens with 4 different impact velocities. The corresponding stress-strain curves are illustrated in Fig.5. The

respective calculation results are listed in the Table 1.

These curves and values indicate that along the cord direction the strength of NCRR is decreasing with the increase of the strain rate. But within the test range the strain rate effect on its stiffness is essentially insignificant. However, compared with the static results, the dynamic strengths and stiffnesses are much lower. On the other hand, the strain values are much larger than those of static tests. So the total strain energy EN of the whole impact process is much greater than the static energy. From above results it indicates that the NCRR is a strain-rate dependent and dynamic toughening material.

Table 2 Strength and total elongation of single nylon cord.

V	V_I	V_{II}	V_{III}	Static
P_{max} N/cord	186.10	175.71	154.25	218.54
ϵ_{max} %	18.66	16.86	15.64	21.7

Table 2 shows the experimental results of the single nylon cord under the impact tension and the static tension. These data indicate that the impact strength of the single nylon cord is lower than that of static case, and also its value is decreasing with the increase of the test velocity, in the same way as the NCRR composite. Contrary to the NCRR, the total impact elongation of the single nylon cord is lower than that of static tension, and within the test velocity range the total elongation of the single nylon cord is sensitive to the strain rate.

Another point worthwhile to mention is that, the static elongation of the NCRR is equal to that of nylon cord, but the impact elongation of the former is much larger than that of latter. The possible explanation of these phenomenon is that composite materials are structures with high redundancy. They are not homogeneous monolithic materials. A cord with a single breakage will lose its load bearing capacity. An NCRR specimen will not fail even if a number of the cords break. The final rupture of the composite is the result of damage accumulation. Under static loading the load redistribution between cords leads to equilibrium as the damage develops. In the case of impact tension, there is not enough time to complete the load redistribution and the damaged cord will sustain load higher than that in static case. That means the damaged cord will have opportunity to suffer more injury and consequently to have larger global strain. At the same time, since the damaged cord sustain the load greater than that under static tension, the global strength of composite under impact will be lower than the static strength.

2. The results of the off-axis impact tests

The test results show that the off-axis tensile properties of NCRR have a few interesting features.

A. The off-axis impact strength is contrary to that of simple tension, higher than the static ones (Fig.6). Obviously,

this is due to the contribution of rubber, which plays an important role during off-axis impact process. As known to all, the rubber is a viscoelastic material, its dynamic modulus G and dynamic strength increase with the loading velocity.

B. Within the test strain rate range of $50 \sim 150 \text{ s}^{-1}$, the effects of the strain rate on the off-axis strength is insignificant as shown in Fig.6 and Fig.7. All the off-axis ($\theta = 45^\circ$) stress-strain curves of specimens impacted with velocities $V_I, V_{II}, V_{III}, V_{IV}$, lie in the same scatter band. The experimental data are listed in Table 3.

C. The impact strength of the NCRR decreases with the increase of the off-axis angle θ .

In Fig.8, three stress-strain curves of the off-axis ($\theta = 45^\circ, 60^\circ, 90^\circ$) specimens, impacted with an approximately the same average strain rate, around 100 s^{-1} ,

Fig. 6 Strengths versus strain rate.

Fig. 7 Stress-strain curves of 45° specimens under three impact velocities.

Table 3 The strengths of NCRR under off-axis impact tension and static tension.

V	0°				30°		
	V_I	V_{II}	V_{III}	V_{IV}	V_I	V_{II}	V_{III}
σ_{max} Mpa	147.84	137.93	135.6	116.14	19.95	17.95	19.2
static σ_{max}	213.2				12.56		

45°			60°			90°		
V_I	V_{II}	V_{III}	V_I	V_{II}	V_{III}	V_I	V_{II}	V_{III}
11.39	10.58	12.21	7.97	9.67	9.80	9.81	10.43	10.9
8.89			7.90			7.50		

Fig. 8 Stress-strain curves of $45^\circ, 60^\circ, 90^\circ$, specimens under and off-axis angle θ . $\dot{\epsilon} \approx 100S^{-1}$.

show that the average elastic modulus \bar{E}^* decreases with increasing of the angle θ . Fig.9 shows that the trend of the strength curves of the off-axis impact tension are same as that of static test. A small deviation from $\theta = 0^\circ$ will cause a drastic drop. However, when $\theta > 45^\circ$, the effect of the off-axis angle is almost negligible.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

From above mentioned analysis of the experimental results, the following conclusions can be reached.

1. Compared with the static tension, the impact strength is lower under simple tension, but higher under the off-axis tension. Here the static strain rate ranges from 10^{-4} ms^{-1} to 10^{-2} ms^{-1} , while the dynamic strain rate ranges from 3 ms^{-1} to 6 ms^{-1} . The strength of a single cord also decreases with the increase of strain rate. This fact confirms that the strength of NCRR under simple impact tension ($\theta = 0^\circ$) is dominated by nylon cord strength. However, under the off-axis impact tension ($\theta > 0^\circ$) the strength of NCRR increases with the increase of strain rate. This is on account of the fact that the rubber as matrix material is a viscoelastic material and its shear modulus G and shear strength increase with the increase of the strain rate and result in the increase of off-axis strength of NCRR with increasing strain rate.

2. The trends of curves of strength versus off-axis angle θ either static or dynamic are the same.

3. Within the test range of high strain rate, $50 \sim 230 \text{ s}^{-1}$, the toughness of the NCRR is higher than the static ones. The total strain energy is greater than that of the static tension.

4. The specially designed force sensor and deformation measuring device are proved to be simple, convenient, and reliable for the impact test on the fiber reinforced rubber. This instrumentation enables us to avoid the indirect measurement. The problem is that, the force sensor is now installed behind the specimen, the material damping of NCRR might reduce the impact force. This shortcoming will be overcome in the future work.

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